

Participant Information Sheet

You have been invited to take part in a research study. Before you decide whether to take part it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please take a moment to read the following information carefully.

What is the study about?

The study documents the personal stories, the life paths, the networks of solidarity and support, and the artistic works by artists from Turkey, who relate to the feeling of exile. With ‘**exile**’ we mean anybody who lives in a place or country that is not his first home and cannot easily return, often due to political, social but also economic reasons. A significant question is the **role of the arts** in understanding political subjectivities emerging from the exilic life situation.

What does the study involve?

The study involves **interviews** with participants who are living in exile or have affinity to the mode of living, and/or who are **at risk** due to their political/ideological ideas, and/or who are involved in artistic production concerning exilic life. Since the project includes talking about conceivably vulnerable topics, **ethical measures are in place to secure your safety**.

Who is organising and funding the research?

The study is funded by the **European Commission** as part of an Individual Marie Skłodowska-Curie Fellowship of Pieter Verstraete, who is the project manager and lead investigator, based at the **Theatre Studies Institute of the Free University Berlin**.

Who has reviewed the study?

This study has been reviewed and approved by the **Central Ethics Committee** of the Free University Berlin. In case of an ethics audit, a detailed documentation of the approval process is kept on file.

Why have I been chosen?

You have been selected because you probably have **first-hand experiences with an exilic life situation and/or related art project**, or you are collaborating with artists with such experiences.

Do I have to take part?

It is up to you to decide whether or not to take part. If you do decide to take part you will be asked to sign a consent form. You are still free to withdraw at any time and without giving a reason.

I am interested in taking part, what do I do next?

Your involvement would be to participate in one or more interviews with the investigator and possibly the assistant when translation is required. The interview will take place at a **convenient time and location for you**, adhering to any safety requirements. It will last for around an hour. We also offer the option of a **telephone or Skype** interview.

What happens to the information?

The data collected from you will be aggregated with the data from other participants in the interviews and this will be analysed and used to produce an online archive, an open-access report, blog posts, presentations and research articles. Before publication, upon request, the transcripts can be shared with you to check whether the transcription is done correctly. When anonymity is strictly called for, your actual name and any information that may lead to your identification will not be mentioned on any occasion, thus respecting your rights and interests. **Please specify in the consent form if you require additional anonymization in the publication of results.**

What about confidentiality and data protection?

All information you may give will be treated in the strictest confidence. The interviewer will take notes and may record the audio, but any information you give during the interview will be fully anonymised. Your audio recording will be given an ID code which will be used instead of your name. All personal data about you will be kept on a password protected database and is strictly confidential. All data will be stored securely in a manner consistent with the standards of data security, protection and legal privacy frameworks defined by German national legislation and the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity. After the research project, these data will be archived and migrated to a separate external hard drive. The raw data will be disposed after two years after the ending date of the research project (1 March 2025) unless you give additional permission to archive.

Who can access the information?

Only the investigator and assistant will have access to the full data. The Central Ethics Committee may require access to check that the study has been conducted in accordance with the approval.

What if I agree to take part and then change my mind?

If after consenting to take part in the interview you subsequently change your mind about participating, **you can withdraw from the study at any time** (including during or after the interview itself). Any data collected from you would not be included in the study.

What are the possible disadvantages or risks of taking part?

We believe that the risks are minimal. We understand that there are many demands on your time and there is some inconvenience in taking part in the interview. You are free at any stage to withdraw from the interview or take time out if you wish. Information that could personally or professionally damage you will not be used. At all times, you have the right to doublecheck your statements and voice concerns of confidentiality or personal risk. You have the right to object to audio and/or video recordings for parts of or the entire interview.

What if something goes wrong?

The risks associated with participation in this research concern the disclosure of a person's identity and insufficient protection of private information, especially when issues of political and/or ideological commentary on the present situation in Turkey are observed. Measures to minimize, if not entirely eliminate these risks will be carefully implemented. If you are harmed by taking part in this research project, there are no special compensation arrangements. If you are harmed due to someone's negligence, then you may have grounds for a legal action but you may have to pay for it.

Who can I complain to?

If you have a complaint regarding anything to do with this study, you can initially approach the lead investigator. If this achieves no satisfactory outcome or if you believe that your rights have been violated in any way, you should then contact **Anika Froehlich**, Team Assistance of Division VI: Research - Legal Council in Research and Transfer:

E-Mail: anika.froehlich@fu-berlin.de

Office: +49 30 838-73621

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Contact for Further Information

If you have any further questions, please feel free to contact the Project Manager, **Dr Pieter Verstraete**:

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Thank your for taking part in the study.

And thank you for your time!